

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
[+91 824 2421566](tel:+918242421566)

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **SKANDA** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**ROLE OF MOBILE BANKING IN THE FINANCIAL INCLUSION**” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management under the supervision of Prof. Sagar Srinivas, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001
Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1986

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. Swathi** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY ON LOAN AND INTERSET RATE OF BANK**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **VINEETH KUMAR S. GATTY** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021- 2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY TO ANALYSE THE POTENTIAL ROLE OF THE COMPANY IN EXPORT & IMPORT: DELTA INFRA LOGISTICS**” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management under the supervision of Mr. Sagar Srinivas, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/10/22

07th July 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SUJITH V (Reg-No-2SU20LS811)** pursuing Masters in Business Administration has successfully completed Internship at **DTDC Express Ltd from 04th April 2022 to 30th June 2022 in the Operations Department.**

During the period of his internship, he has shown keen interest to learn and excel in his field .He was very responsible and committed in his duties and tasks, there by fulfilling our standards and job functions. We believe, if given the opportunity, he will further do better in his work and career.

We wish to express our sincerest gratitude for all his contributions to DTDC Express Ltd and we hope he will be successful in all his future endeavors.

AUTHORIZED SIGNATORY

**MITHUN SHARMA
MANAGER HR**

DTDC Express Limited

CORPORATE OFFICE: DTDC HOUSE, No. 3, Victoria Road, Bangalore - 560 047 Tel.: 080 25365032 / 39 Fax : 080 25514461 CIN No. : UBS110KA1990PLC011089
REGIONAL OFFICE: 2nd Floor, Kummenchery Building, Near KIMS Hospital, Pathadippalam, Changampuzha Nagar PO, Cochin - 682 033 Tel - 0484-4100444

www.dtdc.in

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shamanth Shetty has visited our organization and has collected relevant information for her project, "A study on performance evaluation and competitive strategy of cement company in Kasaragodu with Special reference to ACC ltd".

We hereby certified that the information given in this project is relevant .

For KARLE STEEL
Mr. Padmanabhan K.
Proprietor

Mr. Padmanabhan K.
Branch Manager
Acc Limited

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 8242421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore - 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled “A Study on Impact of Online Trading on Stock Market” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Business Administration is based on the original work done by **SAHANA KARKERA** College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: MANGALORE

Date: 27/1/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
(Dean) Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

**“A STUDY ON PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF SRI
BHAGAVATHI CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD, WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE ON LOANS AND ADVANCE,
MANGALORE”**

**PROJECT SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
THE DEGREE OF**

MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Submitted by

SD ISMAIL UNAIS

Reg. No.: 2SU20MB845

Under the Guidance of

PROF AMITH MENEZES

Associate Professor

Institute of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangalore

July 2022

KASARAGOD SERVICE CO-OPERATIVE BANK

KCB Ltd. No. C 862

Near Municipal Bus Stand,
P. O. Kasaragod- 671121.
Phone: 04994 230296
www.kasaragodscbank.com
Email : kasaragodscbank@gmail.com

Branches:

MAIN BRANCH Ph: 04994 220996
THAYALANGADI Ph: 04994 222996
VIDYANAGAR Ph: 04994 255996
ADKATHBAIL Ph: 04994 230996
MORNING-EVENING Ph: 04994 221996
NELLIKUNNU-KADAPPURAM Ph: 04994 231996

Ref No. _____

Date _____

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that PUNEETH KUMAR C (2SU20MB842) Final year MBA student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore has done the project work entitled A STUDY ON OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF GOLD LOAN IN COOPERATIVE BANK WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE KASARAGOD SERVICE CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD.

He has been provided with necessary guidance and information and he has completed the project work satisfactorily.

Place: Kasaragod

Date: 15.07.2022

Your's faithfully,

Secretary
THE KASARAGOD SERVICE
CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD. No. C. 862
KASARAGOD

KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

II-239/ 1, BETTAMPADY, OLDGATE SULLIA, PIN - 574 239

Date: 12/07/2022

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This is to certify that, **Kum. PRUTHVI C. S REG NO: 2SU20MB841** student of the Final year MBA College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. Has successfully completed her project work titled "**STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION AT KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRY SULLIA**". Successfully completed her project in our industries.

We wish him all the best in the future endeavour

For : KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

Pandha
Proprietor

For KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

Place: Sullia

GEMINI PLASTICS

Fact: SIDCO Industrial Estate - Palayad, Thalassery - 670 661. Phone: 0490 2346548, 2348009
E- mail: gemplast1987@gmail.com

Institute of Management and Commerce

15-07-2022

Srinivas University

Postgraduate

Mangalore - 575001, INDIA

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

Prof. Jayanthi Raj

Institute of Management and Commerce

This is to certify that **MR. VISHNU E. VIJAY** (Reg. No. 2SU20MB863), a Second Year MBA Student of College of Management & Commerce, affiliated to Srinivas University, Mangalore, has undertaken a Project Work in our organisation as part of his curriculum. We had provided all necessary assistance to him in completing the Project Work and he has submitted the Project Report titled, **"A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AT GEMINI PLASTICS, PALAYAD"**. He has carried out the Project Work with good amount of sincerity and commitment.

For GEMINI PLASTICS,

MANAGER

Place: Mangalore

Date: 15/07/2022

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
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Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SHARAN KARKERA (Reg. No. 2SU20LS810)** a student of MBA in Logistics and Supply Chain Management , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship and submitted a report titled “ **Analysis of Problems encountered by clients with reference to Custom Clearance and Documentation process at AMOGHA LOGISTICS ” Mangalore** during the period from **14th April to 15th July 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for AMOGHA LOGISTICS

PARTNER

DATE: 15.07.2022

PLACE : MANGALORE

E-mail : shettynagarajb@ganeshshipping.com
karthikshetty@ganeshshipping.com
agency@ganeshshipping.com
export@ganeshshipping.com
import@ganeshshipping.com
accounts@ganeshshipping.com

ESTD 1979

PHONE Off : 0824-2458429 / 2459219

2459229 / 2458489

Res : 2211189 / 2213442

FAX : 0824 - 2458003

SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

KANARA TOWERS

KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 575 006. INDIA

GSTIN : 29AAFFS2694K1ZK

To Whomsoever It May Concern

This is to Certify that Mr. Preetham – Final Year MBA (LS & SCM) student at Srinivas University (College of Management and commerce), Mangalore, bearing Reg No: 2SU20LS809 has undergone internship training in "A Study on shipping activities & logistics" with reference to Sri Ganesh Shipping Agency, Mangalore from 1st March 2022 to 31st May 2022.

During this period he was found to be sincere, co-operative and hardworking. His character and conduct was good.

We wish him all the best and success in all his future endeavors.

Place : Mangalore

Date : 20.06.2022

for SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

(Karthik Shetty)

CEO

H.O. : Mangalore. Branches : Bangalore • Karwar • Goa

Our Services : Steamer Agency; C&F; Transportation; C.H.A; Stevedoring; Logistics - Project Cargo

**MARUTI
SUZUKI**

ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTAR RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shrdish J shetty , Reg.No. 2SU20MB852, a student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, has succesfully completed his project on "**A study on analysis of loan default and its effect on financial performance of Maruti Suzuki PVT LTD**" in our organization.

during this period of work, we found his conduct was good and sincere effort to study. we appreciate his efforts and interest towards the assigned work.

We wish his all the future endeavours

For Maruti Suzuki Private Limited

UBhat
General Manager
ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTAR RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

**MARUTI
SUZUKI**

ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTAR RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

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For Maruti Suzuki Private Limited

UBhat
General Manager
ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTAR RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

CERTIFICATE

ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಕೃಷಿ ಪತ್ರಿನ ಸಹಕಾರ ಸಂಘ ನಿಯಮಿತ

Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd. Kalasa 577124

☑ ಕಲಸ ಮೂಡುಗರೆ-ಚಿಕ್ಕಮಗಳೂರು 577124 ☑

DRCS No.2444/5-10-76

e-mail:pacskalasa@gmail.com

No. : 76 -/2020-21

ದೂರವಾಣಿ:08263-27 4604

ದಿನಾಂಕ : 26-06-2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to Certify that Mis. SHREYASWINI G (Reg No. 2SU20MB853) Student of Final year M.B.A. at Srinivas University, Pandeshwara, Mangalore has carried out her Project work in our Organization on the subject Kalasa Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd., (PACS) Kalasa 577124, Kalasa Taluck, Chickamagaluru District From the Date 01-03-2022 to 31-03-2022.

During the above Period she has been exposed to the function of finance department and her conduct was found to be good.

We wish her all the best in her Future Endeavour 's.

Sri G.K. Manjappalah,

President,

Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd.,
Kalasa Taluck, Chickamagaluru Dist.

To,

Mis. SHREYASWINI G,
Final year M.B.A.
Reg No. 2SU20MB853,
Srinivas University,
Pandeshwara, Mangalore.

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1986

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Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Sujith S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**NON-PERFORMING ASSET AND DEBT RECOVERY PATTERN IN BANK OF BARODA IN SRINGERI – A STUDY**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhishek N, Research Professor & Research guide,** Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Sujith S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**NON-PERFORMING ASSET AND DEBT RECOVERY PATTERN IN BANK OF BARODA IN SRINGERI – A STUDY**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhishek N, Research Professor & Research guide,** Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

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Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that SURAJ JANARDHAN KOTTAKKAL (2SU20MB857) Final M.B.A student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALURU. He completed his Project work in our company on the topic " EMPIRICAL STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TVS MOTOR COMPANY". Under the guidance of DHANESH.V, Manager, Namans Tvs Motors Kasaragod

During this period his character and conduct was good. We wish all the best in his future endeavors.

For Namans TVS Motors

Manager

Mr. Dhanesh.V

(Circular stamp: Kasaragod, TVS Motors, Authorised Signature)

Place: Kasaragod

Date: 23/4/2022

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD 1988

Institute of Management and
Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. KEERTHAN RAJ

Dean,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. MOHAMMAD HAYAD B (Reg. No: 2SU20MB829)**, is a bonafide student of MBA 4th Semester (2021-22 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. This internship study & project report titled **“An Analysis of non-performance assets Management with special reference to SCDCC Bank, Mangalore”** has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Niyaz Panakaje**, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this Institute.

DEAN

Prof. Keerthan Raj,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Mangalore - 575 001)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1988

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. Swathi** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY ON LOAN AND INTERSET RATE OF BANK**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Dean
Mangaluru - 575 001

KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

II-239/ 1, BETTAMPADY, OLDGATE SULLIA, PIN - 574 239

Ref.....

Date: 12/07/2022

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This is to certify that, **Kum. PRUTHVI C. S REG NO: 2SU20MB841** student of the Final year MBA College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. Has successfully completed her project work titled **“STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION AT KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRY SULLIA**. Successfully completed her project in our industries.

We wish him all the best in the future endeavour

For : KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES
[Signature]
Proprietor

For KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

Place: Sullia

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566**

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/3/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shamanth Shetty has visited our organization and has collected relevant information for her project, "A study on performance evaluation and competitive strategy of cement company in Kasaragodu with Special reference to ACC ltd".

We hereby certified that the information given in this project is relevant .

For KARLE STEEL
K. Padmanabhan
Proprietor
Mr. Padmanabhan K.
Branch Manager
Acc Limited

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA

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Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abdul Najiman** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF CO-OPERATIVE BANK**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Associate Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Institute of Management and Commerce
Dean
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

MHSY
WOS

**MARUTI
SUZUKI**

ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTI RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shrdish J shetty , Reg.No. 2SU20MB852, a student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, has succesfully completed his project on "**A study on analysis of loan default and its effect on financial performance of Maruti Suzuki PVT LTD**" in our organization.

during this period of work, we found his conduct was good and sincere effort to study. we appreciate his efforts and interest towards the assigned work.

We wish his all the future endeavours

For Maruti Suzuki Private Limited

U Bhat
General Manager, sales
ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTI RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
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**Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **VINEETH KUMAR S. GATTY** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021- 2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY TO ANALYSE THE POTENTIAL ROLE OF THE COMPANY IN EXPORT & IMPORT: DELTA INFRA LOGISTICS**” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management under the supervision of Mr. Sagar Srinivas, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/12/22

E-mail : shettynagarajb@ganeshshipping.com
karthikshetty@ganeshshipping.com
agency@ganeshshipping.com
export@ganeshshipping.com
import@ganeshshipping.com
accounts@ganeshshipping.com

ESTD 1979

PHONE Off : 0824-2458429 / 2459219

2459229 / 2458489

Res : 2211189 / 2213442

FAX : 0824 - 2458003

SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

KANARA TOWERS

KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 575 006. INDIA

GSTIN : 29AAFFS2694K1ZK

To Whomsoever It May Concern

This is to Certify that Mr. Preetham – Final Year MBA (LS & SCM) student at Srinivas University (College of Management and commerce), Mangalore, bearing Reg No: 2SU20LS809 has undergone internship training in “A Study on shipping activities & logistics” with reference to Sri Ganesh Shipping Agency, Mangalore from 1st March 2022 to 31st May 2022.

During this period he was found to be sincere, co-operative and hardworking. His character and conduct was good.

We wish him all the best and success in all his future endeavors.

Place : Mangalore

Date : 20.06.2022

for SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

(Karthik Shetty)

CEO

H.O. : Mangalore. Branches : Bangalore • Karwar • Goa

Our Services : Steamer Agency: C&F: Transportation: C.H.A: Stevedoring: Logistics - Project Cargo

Date 20/04/2022

To WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Swathi Bhat P, an MBA student of Srinivas University has successfully completed 1 month of Internship dated 21/02/2022 to 20/03/2022 and completed her project on

" A Study On Best Investment Avenues With a Reference To Motilal Oswal Finacial services" under the guidance of Mr. Vijay Viswas Lobo Remissor "Motilal Oswal Finacial Services" Mangalore Branch for the purpose of the MBA Project.

We wish her success in future

Vijay Viswas Lobo
Motilal Oswal Finacial Services
Remissor ^{HNW} Mangalore

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SHARAN KARKERA (Reg. No. 2SU20LS810)** a student of MBA in Logistics and Supply Chain Management , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship and submitted a report titled “ **Analysis of Problems encountered by clients with reference to Custom Clearance and Documentation process at AMOGHA LOGISTICS ” Mangalore** during the period from **14th April to 15th July 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for AMOGHA LOGISTICS

PARTNER

DATE: 15.07.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

07th July 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. JUBIN K (Reg-No-2SU20LS804)** pursuing Masters in Business Administration has successfully completed Internship at **DTDC Express Ltd** from **04th April 2022 to 30th June 2022** in the **Operations Department**.

During the period of his internship, he has shown keen interest to learn and excel in his field. He was very responsible and committed in his duties and tasks, there by fulfilling our standards and job functions. We believe, if given the opportunity, he will further do better in his work and career.

We wish to express our sincerest gratitude for all his contributions to DTDC Express Ltd and we hope he will be successful in all his future endeavors.

AUTHORIZED SIGNATORY

**MITHUN SHARMA
MANAGER HR**

DTDC Express Limited

CORPORATE OFFICE: DTDC HOUSE, No. 3, Victoria Road, Bangalore - 560 047 Tel.: 080 25365032 / 39 Fax : 080 25514441 CIN No. : U85110KA1990PLC011089
REGIONAL OFFICE: 2nd Floor, Kummenchery Building, Near KIMS Hospital, Pathadippalam, Changampuzha Nagar PO, Cochin - 682 033 Tel - 0484-4100444

www.dtdc.in

CARGO CARE

International (Estd.1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. ANANDHU. R** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

CARGO CARE
International (Estd.1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. AKASH AJI** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “ **A Study on Mergers and Acquisition on Indian Banking Industry**” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by Ms. Navami Nayak(2SU20CM802), Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Dean)
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "*A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND POSITION OF A PRIVATE SECTOR COMPANY AND A PUBLIC SECTOR COMPANY*" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Mr. Sar Aan Jaleel Ahmed(2SU20CM805)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Dean)
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 29/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “EVALUATING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANK OF BARODA AND HDFC BANK, USING CAMEL MODEL” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Shweta. V. Shenoy (2SU20CM806)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001
(Dean)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 28/8/22

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that SURAJ JANARDHAN KOTTAKKAL (2SU20MB857) Final M.B.A student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALURU. He completed his Project work in our company on the topic " EMPIRICAL STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TVS MOTOR COMPANY". Under the guidance of DHANESH.V, Manager, Namans Tvs Motors Kasaragod

During this period his character and conduct was good. We wish all the best in his future endeavors.

For Namans TVS Motors

Manager

Mr. Dhanesh.V

(Circular stamp: TVS Motors Kasaragod, Authorised Signature)

Place: Kasaragod

Date: 23/4/2022

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD 1988

Institute of Management and
Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. KEERTHAN RAJ

Dean,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. MOHAMMAD HAYAD B (Reg. No: 2SU20MB829)**, is a bonafide student of MBA 4th Semester (2021-22 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. This internship study & project report titled **“An Analysis of non-performance assets Management with special reference to SCDCC Bank, Mangalore”** has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Niyaz Panakaje**, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this Institute.

DEAN

Prof. Keerthan Raj,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Mangalore - 575 001)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1988

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. Swathi** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY ON LOAN AND INTERSET RATE OF BANK**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Dean
Mangaluru - 575 001

KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

II-239/ 1, BETTAMPADY, OLDGATE SULLIA, PIN - 574 239

Ref.....

Date: 12/07/2022

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This is to certify that, **Kum. PRUTHVI C. S REG NO: 2SU20MB841** student of the Final year MBA College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. Has successfully completed her project work titled **“STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION AT KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRY SULLIA**. Successfully completed her project in our industries.

We wish him all the best in the future endeavour

For : KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES
[Signature]
Proprietor

For KAMILA CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES

Place: Sullia

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566**

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/3/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shamanth Shetty has visited our organization and has collected relevant information for her project, "A study on performance evaluation and competitive strategy of cement company in Kasaragodu with Special reference to ACC ltd".

We hereby certified that the information given in this project is relevant .

For KARLE STEEL
K. Padmanabhan
Proprietor
Mr. Padmanabhan K.
Branch Manager
Acc Limited

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “A STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO DELTA HOUSE” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Vallisha. K (2SU20MB862)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Abdul Najiman** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF CO-OPERATIVE BANK**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Associate Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Institute of Management and Commerce
Dean
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

MHSV
WOS

**MARUTI
SUZUKI**

ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTI RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shrdish J shetty , Reg.No. 2SU20MB852, a student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, has succesfully completed his project on "**A study on analysis of loan default and its effect on financial performance of Maruti Suzuki PVT LTD**" in our organization.

during this period of work, we found his conduct was good and sincere effort to study. we appreciate his efforts and interest towards the assigned work.

We wish his all the future endeavours

For Maruti Suzuki Private Limited

U Bhat
General Manager, Sales
ARAVIND BUILDING, BALMATTI RD,
HAMPANKATTA, MANGALURU,
KARNATAKA 575001

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **VINEETH KUMAR S. GATTY** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021- 2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**A STUDY TO ANALYSE THE POTENTIAL ROLE OF THE COMPANY IN EXPORT & IMPORT: DELTA INFRA LOGISTICS**” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management under the supervision of Mr. Sagar Srinivas, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/12/22

E-mail : shettynagarajb@ganeshshipping.com
karthikshetty@ganeshshipping.com
agency@ganeshshipping.com
export@ganeshshipping.com
import@ganeshshipping.com
accounts@ganeshshipping.com

ESTD 1979

PHONE Off : 0824-2458429 / 2459219
2459229 / 2458489
Res : 2211189 / 2213442
FAX : 0824 - 2458003

SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

KANARA TOWERS
KOTTARA CHOWKI, MANGALORE - 575 006. INDIA
GSTIN : 29AAFFS2694K1ZK

To Whomsoever It May Concern

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During this period he was found to be sincere, co-operative and hardworking. His character and conduct was good.

We wish him all the best and success in all his future endeavors.

Place : Mangalore

Date : 20.06.2022

for SRI GANESH SHIPPING AGENCY

(Karthik Shetty)
CEO

H.O. : Mangalore. Branches : Bangalore • Karwar • Goa

Our Services : Steamer Agency: C&F: Transportation: C.H.A: Stevedoring: Logistics - Project Cargo

Date 20/04/2022

To WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Swathi Bhat P, an MBA student of Srinivas University has successfully completed 1 month of Internship dated 21/02/2022 to 20/03/2022 and completed her project on

" A Study On Best Investment Avenues With a Reference To Motilal Oswal Finacial services" under the guidance of Mr. Vijay Viswas Lobo Remissor "Motilal Oswal Finacial Services" Mangalore Branch for the purpose of the MBA Project.

We wish her success in future

Vijay Viswas Lobo
Motilal Oswal Finacial Services
Remissor ^{HW} Mangalore

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SHARAN KARKERA (Reg. No. 2SU20LS810)** a student of MBA in Logistics and Supply Chain Management , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed his Internship and submitted a report titled “ **Analysis of Problems encountered by clients with reference to Custom Clearance and Documentation process at AMOGHA LOGISTICS ” Mangalore** during the period from **14th April to 15th July 2022**.

During the tenure of the Project work he has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing him all the best in his future endeavours.

for AMOGHA LOGISTICS

PARTNER

DATE: 15.07.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

07th July 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. JUBIN K (Reg-No-2SU20LS804)** pursuing Masters in Business Administration has successfully completed Internship at **DTDC Express Ltd** from **04th April 2022 to 30th June 2022** in the **Operations Department**.

During the period of his internship, he has shown keen interest to learn and excel in his field. He was very responsible and committed in his duties and tasks, there by fulfilling our standards and job functions. We believe, if given the opportunity, he will further do better in his work and career.

We wish to express our sincerest gratitude for all his contributions to DTDC Express Ltd and we hope he will be successful in all his future endeavors.

AUTHORIZED SIGNATORY

**MITHUN SHARMA
MANAGER HR**

DTDC Express Limited

CORPORATE OFFICE: DTDC HOUSE, No. 3, Victoria Road, Bangalore - 560 047 Tel.: 080 25365032 / 39 Fax : 080 25514441 CIN No. : U85110KA1990PLC011089
REGIONAL OFFICE: 2nd Floor, Kummenchery Building, Near KIMS Hospital, Pathadippalam, Changampuzha Nagar PO, Cochin - 682 033 Tel - 0484-4100444

www.dtdc.in

CARGO CARE

International (Estd.1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. ANANDHU. R** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

CARGO CARE
International (Estd.1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. AKASH AJI** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

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DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Dean)
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "*A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND POSITION OF A PRIVATE SECTOR COMPANY AND A PUBLIC SECTOR COMPANY*" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Mr. Sar Aan Jaleel Ahmed(2SU20CM805)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Dean)
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 29/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

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DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001
(Dean)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 28/8/22

Patspin India Ltd,
Para kanjikode Rd,
Kanjikode east P o.
Palakkad -672016

12.03.2022
SMRL/PJT/6194

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Mohammed Shahil P K, Reg number 2SU20MB831, MBA student of Srinivas university Mangalore, Karnataka has undergone a project work regarding 'EMPLOYEE WELFARE MEASURES AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE LOYALTY' in our company and successfully completed during April-June.

Ratheesh
Asst. Manager-HR

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. LAKSHITHA . P (Reg. No. 2SU20LS805)** a student of MBA in Logistics and Supply Chain Management , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed her Internship and submitted a report titled “ **Analytical study on Import and Export procedure at AMOGHA LOGISTICS ” Mangalore** during the period from 14th April to 15th July 2022.

During the tenure of the Project work she has been very keen & resourceful.

Wishing her all the best in his future endeavours.

for AMOGHA LOGISTICS

PARTNER

DATE: 15.07.2022
PLACE : MANGALORE

Hasan Hajee & Co

STEVEDORES, C&F AGENTS, CUSTOM HOUSE AGENTS, STEAMER AGENTS, HANDLING & TRANSPORT CONTRACTORS

20/8/674, "KHADEEJA COURT", Bunder, Mangalore - 575 001.
☎ : 0824-2420737/2420837/4255637/4255737, Fax: 0091-824-2420
E-MAIL: office@hasanhajee.com; admin@hasanhajee.com; Web: www.hasanhajee.com

Date 14.07.2022

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Mehammod Muzammil (2SU20LS806) studying in Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar was working with us as a Trainee Supervisor in Clearing and Forwarding department from 03rd April 2022 to 03rd July 2022.

He has been trained in documentation and operations in Clearing & Forwarding, Stevedoring and specifically in Custom House Department.

During the internship period he was sincere, hard working and showed keen interest to learn.

The involvement and sustained effort put by him were highly appreciable, which helped him do well.

We wish all the best in his career ahead.

For, Hasan Hajee & Co

Manager

Delta Infralogistics (worldwide) Limited

(Formerly HML Agencies Pvt. Ltd.)

Delta House, 6th Floor, Bangra Kular Road, Kular, Mangalore - 575 013, INDIA

+91 824 2454811/2/3 info@groupdelta.in, deltainfralogistics@gmail.com

www.groupdelta.in

CIN No. U63090KA1998PLC023501

Ref: DIWL/410/58/2022-23

Date: 12.07.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

Sub: Internship Completion Certificate

This is to certify that **Mr. Mohammed Baqir, MBA (LS & SCM) (USN 2SU20LS807)** from Srinivas University, GHS Road, Mangalore- 575001 has successfully completed his internship on "**Logistics**" under the supervision of Mr. Mohammed Aris, Sr. Asst. from 10.03.2022 to 09.06.2022.

During this period he was found to be sincere, hardworking and demonstrated positive attitude towards achieving his objectives.

On behalf of Delta Infralogistics (Worldwide) Pvt. Ltd, we wish him all the success in his future endeavor.

For Delta Infralogistics (Worldwide) Ltd.

Director

AUTHORISED
ECONOMIC
OPERATOR

AN ISO 9001:2015 CERTIFIED COMPANY

SHIPPING

CHA

LOGISTICS

WAREHOUSING

CONSTRUCTION

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammed Zafar Schemnad, bearing Reg.No 2SU20LS808** student from Srinivas University Instituion of Management & Commerce has done his internship in "Delivery Department" at our Mannagudda Distribution Centre Mangalore from 25.03.2022 to 24.06.2022.

During his internship he was found hard working and taking keen interest on his assignment.

We wish him best of luck.

For **PRAKASH RETAIL PVT.LTD,**

B.N.AMIN
GENERAL MANAGER HR

CERTIFICATE

ಪ್ರಾಥಮಿಕ ಕೃಷಿ ಪತ್ರಿನ ಸಹಕಾರ ಸಂಘ ನಿಯಮಿತ

Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd. Kalasa 577124

☑ ಕಲಸ ಮೂಡಿಗೆರೆ-ಕಾಸಾಳು 577124 ☑

DRCS No.2444/5-10-76

e-mail:pacskalasa@gmail.com

No. : 76 -/2020-21

ದೂರವಾಣಿ:08263-27 4604

ದಿನಾಂಕ : 26-06-2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to Certify that Mis. SHREYASWINI G (Reg No. 2SU20MB853) Student of Final year M.B.A. at Srinivas University, Pandeshwara, Mangalore has carried out her Project work in our Organization on the subject Kalasa Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd., (PACS) Kalasa 577124, Kalasa Taluck, Chickamagaluru District From the Date 01-03-2022 to 31-03-2022.

During the above Period she has been exposed to the function of finance department and her conduct was found to be good.

We wish her all the best in her Future Endeavour 's.

Sri G.K. Manjappaiah,

President,

Primary Agricultural Credit Co-Operative Society Ltd.,
Kalasa Taluck, Chickamagaluru Dist.

To,

Mis. SHREYASWINI G,

Final year M.B.A.

Reg No. 2SU20MB853,

Srinivas University,

Pandeshwara, Mangalore.

Ph: 0820 - 2573424

ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ ವಿವಿಧೋದ್ದೇಶ ಸೌಹಾರ್ದ ಸಹಕಾರಿ (ಸಿ.)

ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು ಆವಳು, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ಕೆ.ಆರ್.ನಗರ - 576101

D. ನಂ. 3573 / 14 - 15

ಸ್ಥಳ : _____

ತಾರೀಖು : _____

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Miss Swathi Shetty MBA Student Studing at Srinivas Institute of Management, has successfully completed 15 Days Research work at our Souhardha Sahakari Society. During the period of Research work she was found Punctual, hardworking and inquisitive.

ಪದಾಧಿಕಾರಿ

ಸ್ವರಾಜ್ ವಿವಿಧೋದ್ದೇಶ ಸೌಹಾರ್ದ ಸಹಕಾರಿ (ಸಿ.)
ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು ಆವಳು, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು, ಕೆ.ಆರ್.ನಗರ.

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1988

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Sujith S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**NON-PERFORMING ASSET AND DEBT RECOVERY PATTERN IN BANK OF BARODA IN SRINGERI – A STUDY**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhishek N, Research Professor & Research guide**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 8242421566**

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore - 575001**

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled “A Study on Impact of Online Trading on Stock Market” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Business Administration is based on the original work done by **SAHANA KARKERA** College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: MANGALORE

Date: 23/1/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
(Dean) Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “ **A Study on Mergers and Acquisition on Indian Banking Industry**” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by Ms. Navami Nayak(2SU20CM802), Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

CARGO CARE

International (Estd.1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. AKASH AJI** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

CARGO CARE
International (Estd. 1986)

LICENCED CUSTOMS BROKERS

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION OF 4 MONTHS INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Mr. ANANDHU. R** has completed the Industrial Internship at Cargo Care International for a period from 21.03.2022 till 16.07.2022.

This company is engaged in Clearing, Forwarding, Transportation, Import and Export works. During the tenure he was found to be diligent and hard working and conduct of him was good.

For CARGO CARE INTERNATIONAL

Authorized Signatory

Date : 16.07.2022

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**EVALUATING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANK OF BARODA AND HDFC BANK, USING CAMEL MODEL**” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Ms. Shweta. V. Shenoy (2SU20CM806)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001
(Dean)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 28/12/22

28.06.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Damini S** bearing Reg No 2SU20LS803 student from Srinivas University Institution of Management & Commerce has done her internship on "**Merchandise Department**" in our Mannagudda Distribution Centre Mangalore from 25.03.2022 to 24.06.2022.

During the internship she was taking keen interest in learning those subjects connected to her studies. She was found hard working and sincere.

We wish her every success.

For **PRAKASH RETAIL PVT.LTD,**

B.N.AMIN
GENERAL MANAGER HR

07th July 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. SUJITH V (Reg-No-2SU20LS811)** pursuing Masters in Business Administration has successfully completed Internship at **DTDC Express Ltd** from **04th April 2022 to 30th June 2022** in the **Operations Department**.

During the period of his internship, he has shown keen interest to learn and excel in his field. He was very responsible and committed in his duties and tasks, there by fulfilling our standards and job functions. We believe, if given the opportunity, he will further do better in his work and career.

We wish to express our sincerest gratitude for all his contributions to DTDC Express Ltd and we hope he will be successful in all his future endeavors.

AUTHORIZED SIGNATORY

**MITHUN SHARMA
MANAGER HR**

DTDC Express Limited

CORPORATE OFFICE: DTDC HOUSE, No. 3, Victoria Road, Bangalore - 560 047 Tel.: 080 25365832 / 39 Fax : 080 25514461 CIN No. : UB5110KA1990PLC011089
REGIONAL OFFICE: 2nd Floor, Kummenchery Building, Near KIMS Hospital, Pathadippalam, Changampuzha Nagar PO, Cochin - 682 033 Tel - 0484-4100444

www.dtdc.in

GEMINI PLASTICS

Fact: SIDCO Industrial Estate - Palayad, Thalassery - 670 661. Phone: 0490 2346548, 2348009
E- mail: gemplast1987@gmail.com

Institute of Management and Commerce
15-07-2022
Srinivas University
Fardesherar,
Mangalore - 575001, INDIA

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

Prof. Keerthi Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce

This is to certify that **MR. VISHNU E. VIJAY (Reg. No. 2SU20MB863)**, a Second Year MBA Student of College of Management & Commerce, affiliated to Srinivas University, Mangalore, has undertaken a Project Work in our organisation as part of his curriculum. We had provided all necessary assistance to him in completing the Project Work and he has submitted the Project Report titled, **"A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AT GEMINI PLASTICS, PALAYAD"**. He has carried out the Project Work with good amount of sincerity and commitment.

For GEMINI PLASTICS,

MANAGER

Place: Mangalore
Date: 15/07/2022

**“A STUDY ON PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF SRI
BHAGAVATHI CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD, WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE ON LOANS AND ADVANCE,
MANGALORE”**

**PROJECT SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
THE DEGREE OF**

MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Submitted by

SD ISMAIL UNAIS

Reg. No.: 2SU20MB845

Under the Guidance of

PROF AMITH MENEZES

Associate Professor

Institute of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangalore

July 2022

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "*A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND POSITION OF A PRIVATE SECTOR COMPANY AND A PUBLIC SECTOR COMPANY*" submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by **Mr. Sar Aan Jaleel Ahmed(2SU20CM805)**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Abhinandan Kulal, Assistant professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
(Dean)
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date: 29/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
[+91 824 2421566](tel:+918242421566)

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **SKANDA** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**ROLE OF MOBILE BANKING IN THE FINANCIAL INCLUSION**” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management under the supervision of Prof. Sagar Srinivas, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001
Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

KASARAGOD SERVICE CO-OPERATIVE BANK

Ltd. No. C 862

Near Municipal Bus Stand,
P. O. Kasaragod- 671121.
Phone: 04994 230296
www.kasaragodscbank.com
Email : kasaragodscbank@gmail.com

Branches:

MAIN BRANCH Ph: 04994 220996
THAYALANGADI Ph: 04994 222996
VIDYANAGAR Ph: 04994 255996
ADKATHBAIL Ph: 04994 230996
MORNING-EVENING Ph: 04994 221996
NELLIKUNHU-KADAPPURAM Ph: 04994 231996

Ref No.

Date _____

CERTIFICATE

*This is to certify that PUNEETH KUMAR C (25U20MB842) Final year MBA student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore has done the project work entitled **A STUDY ON OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF GOLD LOAN IN COOPERATIVE BANK WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE KASARAGOD SERVICE CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD.***

He has been provided with necessary guidance and information and he has completed the project work satisfactorily.

Place: Kasaragod

Date: 15.07.2022

Your's faithfully,

Secretary
THE KASARAGOD SERVICE
CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD. No.C.862
KASARAGOD

UNITY
Hospital
— expect life

02.06.2022

UH/HRD/685/22

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Ashwini A.V**, a Student of 2nd year MBA, Srinivas University, Mangalore has completed a project study on the topic "A study on Employee Satisfaction at Unity Hospital" during May 2022.

Unity Hospital is a NABH Accredited 250 bedded Hospital and is a Health Promotion Centre with multi-specialties.

We wish **Ms. Ashwini** every success in all her future endeavors.

A NABH Accredited Hospital

Registered Office : "Unity Care and Health Services Pvt. Ltd."
R.B. No.: 535, Falnir Road, Mangalore - 575 002, India.

+91 824 - 4245555/2432770 (6 Lines), Fax : +91 824 - 2432691, O.R.D. : +91 824 - 2431555/2433401 (3 lines)
Email : info@unityhospital.in Website : www.unityhospital.in
CIN : U85110KA2000PTC027880 PAN : AAACU6793M GSTIN : 29AAACU6793M1ZH

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. ASPAK K S** bearing Register Number **2SU20MB809** is a bonafide student of Master of Business Administration (MBA) course of this institute (2020-2022 batch). The Internship Project titled **“A STUDY ON PREDICTION OF FINANCIAL DISTRESS OF SELECTED IT COMPANIES”** is prepared by him under the guidance of **DR. ABHINANDAN** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Business Administration (MBA).

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/7/22

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

BARAKA OVERSEAS TRADERS

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. BASHEER HILAL, bearing REG.NO. 2SU20MB810 student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, Pandeswar, Mangalore, had done a project report on "A STUDY ON CREDIT MANAGEMENT AND COST CONTROL WITH REFERENCE TO BARAKA OVERSEAS TRADERS" towards the partial fulfillment of the award of master of Business Administration during the period of 10th June 2022 to 25th June 2022.

During the above period his conduct was found to be good and satisfactory.

We wish all the best for his future endeavors.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 28.06.2022

For Baraka Overseas Traders

Manager

POST BOX NO. 1204, BEACH ROAD, ULLAL - 575 020 MANGALORE (INDIA)
Phone : 91-824-2468801 / 2468805 / 2467425
e-mail : indofisheries@gmail.com / barakaoverseas@gmail.com
GSTIN : 29AABFB1889P125

KARAMOGARU ROOFINGS

KAJILA, THENKULIPADI VILLAGE,
MALALI POST, MANGALORE - 574151
Mob : 9448627273, 8971340273
Email : karamogaru@gmail.com
Office : 0824-2447273, 8105079273

To whomsoever it may concern

This is to certify that Ms. Krithika, Reg. No 2SU20MB820, a student of college of management and studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed her project internship on "EFFECT OF GST ON SALES OF KARAMOGARU ROOFINGS " in our organization.

During this period of work, we found her conduct was good and sincere effort to study. We appreciate her efforts and interest towards the assigned work

We wish her all the best for all future endeavours

For Karamogaru Roofings

General Manager

KARAMOGARU ROOFING
D. No. 8-65/3B, Kajila, Malali Post
MANGALORE - 574 151

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+918242421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute Of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore - 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is certify that **Keerthana K** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This project report titled “ **A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AT KSAK AND SONS CASHEW FACTORY KASARGOD**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Sonia Noronha, professor** , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Place: Mangalore

Date

27/2/22

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

No. KWP/HR/02/2022-223

11th June, 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. INDUSHA N** Reg No. 2SU20MB817, MBA student of Srinivas University Mangalore - 575001 has undergone project work on "A study on workers participation in management with special reference to Kanara Wood & Plywood Industries Ltd." in our establishment successfully as part of MBA course during the year 2021-2022.

We wish her all success in her future endeavours.

For **KANARA WOOD & PLYWOOD INDUSTRIES LTD.**

Authorized Signatory

Kanara Wood & Plywood Industries Ltd.

Regd. & Head Office : Jeppu, Mangalore - 575 002, India
Phone : 0824-2414256 / 2418858 • Fax : 91-824 2418775 • Grams : KENWOOD
Website : www.kenwoodply.com • E-mail : kanarawood@rediffmail.com
TIN : 29510276230 CST : 30450548 Dt. 1-4-73

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD 1989

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Karthik K A is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled "A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF MUTHOOT FINANCE LIMITED IN PROMOTING FINANCIAL INCLUSION" has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr. Niyaz Panakaje, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date:

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that HARSHITHA BR is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**IMPACT OF DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM ON TRUST AND CONTINUOUS INTENSION**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr Niyaz Panakaje, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

Place: Mangalore
Date:

ASHTAVAIDYAN THAIKKATTU MOOSS
VAIDYARATNAM

Since 1941

12.03.2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms Gowri N K, Reg number 2SU20MB815, MBA student of Srinivas university Mangalore, Karnataka has undergone a project work regarding 'employee retention' in our company and successfully completed during April-June.

RAMESHAN P T,
HR Manager

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof.Keerthan Raj

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify **Mr.Franoy Peter Vaz** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4TH semester (2021-2022) at Institute of Management and commerce Srinivas University Pandeshwar. This project report title “Study on Work Life Balance, Quality of Work Life and Well Being of Women Nurses with Reference to Private Hospitals at Mangalore”, has been prepared by him in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr.Sonia Noronha, Professor**, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute .

Prof.Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Dean
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ವಿಕಾಸ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕ್
 ಸಂವತ್ಸರ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕ್ ಕುರಿತು ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣ

Karnataka Vikas Grameena Bank
 Head office Dharwad

REF NO. 02/2022-23

Date: 14/07/2022

CERTIFICATE

Ms CHAITHALI a student of Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. Studying Master of Business Administration with registration number 2SU20MB813 has done the project report on "A STUDY ON NON-PERFORMING ASSETS OF KARNATAKA VIKASA GRAMEENA BANK - ULTHOOR" as part of her study. During the course of this project she was provided with required information.

PLACE : ULTHOOR
 DATE : 14.07.2022

For Karnataka Vikas Grameena Bank
[Signature]
 Manager, Office - Ulthoor
 Kundapur, Dist. Udupi

☎ 18004251666
 08254-228845

ULTHOOR BRANCH
 576231

Place: Mangalore

Date:

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**

**SAMADRA GHANA
ESTD 1988**

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University,
Pandeshwar
Mangalore -575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **BONNY BOSE** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled **A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ADVERTISEMENT TOWARDS THE PURCHASE OF MERIBOY ICE CREAM** has been prepared by her impartial fulfillments of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD 1988

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University

Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001, INDIA

+91 824 2421566

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. Bhoomika B S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “**FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MRPL**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Abhinandan Kulal**, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

DEAN

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

TO WHOMEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. POOJA K has visited our organization and has collected relevant information for her project, "A study on performance analysis of leather company in Mangluru with special reference to Bata Limited".

We hereby certified that the information given in this project is relevant .

Mr. Rajesh Gaikwad
Bata India Limited
Branch - Mangalore
Commercial Complex, Ks Rao
Road, Mangalore - 575001 (Near
City Center Mall, Hampankatta)
Tel. No 0824222247
GSTIN: 29AABE01059021

Institute of Management and
Commerce Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore-575001, INDIA
+91 8242421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore-575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled “**A STUDY ON SECURITY CONCERNS FOR ONLINE TRANSACTIONS WITH REFERENCE TO E-COMMERCE USERS**” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Business Administration is based on the original work done by **MS.NIDHI POOJARY** Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: MANGALORE

Date: 27/11/21

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 8242421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore - 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled “A STUDY ON BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE OF INDIVIDUALS DURING FINANCIAL AND NON FINANCIAL INVESTMENT DECISIONS WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALORE CITY” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Business Administration is based on the original work done by Ms. Namratha N Amin College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Place: MANGALORE

Date: 27/7/22

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

ಭಟ್ಟಕ ಕೃಷಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಹಕಾರಿ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕ್ ನಿಯಮಿತ

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಕಛೇರಿ : ಭಟ್ಟಕ (ಉ.ಕ)

BHATKAL AGRIL & RURAL DEVELOPMENT CO-OP. BANK LTD.,

ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಛೇರಿ : 08385-227559	ಶಾಖೆ : 08385-227559	ಪುಸ್ತಕ : 08385-227559	ಉಪ : 08385-227559	ಶಾಖೆ : 08385-227559
ಕುಟುಂಬ : 08385-227559	ಸಹಕಾರಿ : 08385-227559	ಸಹಕಾರಿ : 08385-227559	ಸಹಕಾರಿ : 08385-227559	ಸಹಕಾರಿ : 08385-227559

Project work | 2022-23

ದಿನಾಂಕ : 11/07/2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to Certify that Ms. Namrata Mastappa Naik student of M B A Final Sem at collage of "Management And Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. Done the project on "An Evaluation Of Agriculture Loan And its Impact On Rural Development With Reference To Bhatkal Agriculture And Rural Development Co-Operative Bank Ltd. Bhatkal" as part of her study. During the course of his project he was provided with all the materials and information.

Place : Bhatkal
 Date : 11.07.2022

For THE B.A.R.D.C. BANK LTD
 H.O. BHATKAL

 Asst. G. Manager

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Murshid Abdulla. is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “A study on financial efficiency & service analysis with reference to Sri Ramakrishna Credit Cooperative society, Mangalore” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr Niyaz Panakaje, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 27/2/22

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
(Dean)
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD 1988

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University

Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001, INDIA

+91 824 2421566

Prof. KEERTHAN RAJ

Dean

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammed Rizwan (Reg. No: 2SU20MB833)**, is a bonafide student of MBA 4th Semester (2021-22 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore. This internship study & project report titled “A Study on financial analysis with special reference to shri bhagavathi co-operative bank, Mangalore” has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the suovision of **Dr. Niyaz Panakaje**, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this Institute.

Prof. Keerthan Raj,
DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Place; Mangalore

Date; 22/11/22

KVR DREAM VEHICLES PVT.LTD.

TATA MOTORS

No:KVRD/KSD/09(PJT)

Date:17/03/2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERNS

It is to certify that Mr. MOHAMMED SHIHABUDEEN Reg number 2SU20MB832, MBA student of
Kannada University Mangalore, Karnataka has undergone a project work regarding "A STUDY ON JOB
SATISFACTION LEVEL AMONG THE EMPLOYEES" in our company and successfully completed
during June-July

For KVR DREAM VEHICLES PVT.LTD

MANAGER(HDR)

KVR Dream vehicles (p) ltd

Kasarkode

An ISO 9001:2015
ISO 14001:2015 &
ISO 45001: 2018
COMPANY

ಕೆಪಿಒಸಿಎಲ್ ಲಿಮಿಟೆಡ್
(ಭಾರತ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಉದ್ಯಮ)
ಪಾಢುಬುರು, ಮಂಗಲೂರು - 575 010
CIN - L13100KA1976PLC002974
ದೂರವಾಣಿ: 0824-2403225
ಫ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ : 0824-2407422
ಇ-ಮೇಲ್ : kioclmlr@kioclltd.com
ವೆಬ್‌ಸೈಟ್ : www.kioclltd.in

के आई ओ सी एल लिमिटेड
(भारत सरकार का एक उद्यम)
पणंबूर, मंगलूर - 575 010
CIN - L13100KA1976PLC002974
टेलिफोन : 0824-2403225
फैक्स : 0824-2407422
ई-मेल : kioclmlr@kioclltd.com
वेबसाईट : www.kioclltd.in

KIOCL LIMITED

(A Government of India Enterprise)
Panambur, MANGALURU - 575 010
CIN - L13100KA1976PLC002974
Telephone: 0824-2403225
Fax : 0824-2407422
E-mail : kioclmlr@kioclltd.com
Website : www.kioclltd.in

No. HR/M/014/2C/2022
Date:28.06.2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Supritha H K, Reg. No.2SU20MB856, Student of final year MBA in Srinivas Institute of Management and Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore has carried out her project work in our organization on the subject " A Study on Financial Analysis and Social Accounting with Special Reference of KIOCL Limited" at Finance Department, KIOCL Limited, Panambur, Mangalore - 575 010, from 01.03.2022 to 31.03.2022.

During the above period, she has been exposed to the functions of the Finance Department and her conduct was found to be GOOD.

(Murgesh S) 25/6/22

Sr. Manager (HR & Coord)

ಮುರ್ಗೇಶ್ ಎಸ್. / MURGESH .S

ವರಿಷ್ಠ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿ (ಮಾನವ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮನ್ವಯ)
Senior Manager (HR & Coord)

ಕೆ.ಐ.ಓ.ಸಿ.ಎಲ್. ಲಿಮಿಟೆಡ್ / KIOCL Limited

ಪಾಢುಬುರು, ಮಂಗಲೂರು / Panambur, Mangalore - 575 010

To

Ms. Supritha H K
Final year MBA,
Reg.No. 2SU20MB856
Srinivas Institute of Management and Studies, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore.

ನೋಂದಾಯಿತ ಕಾರ್ಯಾಲಯ : 2ನೇ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಕೊರಮಂಗಲ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು - 560 034

पंजीकृत कार्यालय : II ब्लॉक, कोरमंगला, बेंगलूर - 560 034.

Registered Office : II Block, Koramangala, Bengaluru - 560 034.

ಪರಿಸರ-ಸಮ್ಮುಖ್ಯತೆ, ಸಮ್ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪಾರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಕೆ - ಹಮಾರ ಲಕ್ಷ್ಯ ಹಮಾರಿ ನಿಟ್ಟಾ ECOLOGY - OUR MISSION OUR OBSESSION

Date:20/06/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER MAY CONCERN

This is certifying that **Mr. Sooraj B, Reg.No.2SU20MB854**, a student of **Srinivas University institute of Management and commerce Mangalore**, has successfully completed his project study on the topic entitled "**A study of Fundamental and competitive Analysis of trading in Mangalore city reference to Selected stocks in Kotak Securities Ltd**" in our organisations.

During this period of work, we found her conduct was good and sincere effort to study. We appreciate her effort and interest towards the assigned work.

We wish her all the best for all future endeavours.

For Kotak securities Ltd

Sandeep V

Branch Manager

Kotak Securities Ltd.
CIN. U99999MH1994PLC134051
10/7, Umiya Landmark
1st Floor, Lavelle Road
Bangalore - 560001
Karnataka,

T +91 80 6620 3600 / 601
F +91 80 6612 8180
www.kotaksecurities.com

Registered Office :
27 BKC, C 27, G Block
Bandra Kurla Complex
Bandra (E), Mumbai - 400 051

T +91 22 43360000
F +91 22 67132430
Toll Free: 1800000000
www.kotaksecurities.com

12.03.2022

Ref: EETIPL/HR/IT/02/2022

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that Ms. **Thrupthi U C** with register no **2SU20MB861** studying in second year, 4th semester MBA-HR at Collage of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Dakshina Kannada District, has done 15 days **training on a study on Employee Job satisfaction survey** and HR related topics in our Industry Exa Thermometrics India Pvt Ltd an Amphenol Company From 21st February to 12th March 2022. The Company is an export oriented unit into the manufacturing of Temperature sensing devices. As part of the internship program, She was placed with all our HR and administration, EHS/EMS, and all technical departments.

During this period, we found her punctual, sincere, and hardworking and she has taken proper initiative and efforts towards completing training and the Project.

She deserves all encouragement

We wish success in her career.

For Exa Thermometrics India Pvt Ltd., an Amphenol company.

Bengaluru
560 100

Chitrakala P

HR Manager.

Mob: 9986504955

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. Ruchita S Shetty is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF RISK MANAGEMENT ON PROFITABILITY OF THE SIRSI URBAN SAHAKARI BANK LIMITED” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Prof. Amith Menezes, Associate Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

CERTIFICATE

ರ.ಸಂ.೩೬೦.೬೬೦. 178/72-73

ಸ್ಥಾಪನೆ : 04-10-1972

ಭಟ್ಕಳ ಕೃಷಿ ಹಾಗೂ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಸಹಕಾರಿ ಬ್ಯಾಂಕ್ ನಿಯಮಿತ

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಕಛೇರಿ : ಭಟ್ಕಳ (ಉ.ಕ)

BHATKAL AGRIL & RURAL DEVELOPMENT CO-OP. BANK LTD.,

ಶಾಖೆಗಳು : ಮುಖ್ಯಕಛೇರಿ : 08385 227559, 222248 | ಆಕೃತಿ : 08385 227559 | ಸ್ವೀಕೃತಿ : 08385 227559 | ಕಾರ್ಯ : 08385 227559 | ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : 08385 227559 | ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : 08385 227559 | ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ : 08385 227559

ಉಲ್ಲೇಖ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆ :

23

ದಿನಾಂಕ : 06/06/2022

CERTIFICATE

Ms. SAHANA MANJUNATH NAIK a student of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, College of Management and Commerce, Pandeshwar, Manglore Studying M B A Degree with Registration No. 2SUU20MB847 was done the project on "A STUDY ON NON PERFORMING ASSETS OF BHATKAL AGRIL & RURAL DEVELOPMENT CO-OPERATIVE BANK LTD" as part of her study. During the course of his project she was provided with all the materials and information.

Place : Bhatkal
Date : 06.06.2022

General Manager
GENERAL MANAGER
B.A.R.D.C. BANK LTD.
H.O. BHATKAL

 08385-227559, 222248

 bardcbankhatkal@gmail.com
bardcbankhatkal@rediffmail.com

 H.O. BHATKAL - 581 320. (U.K.)

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**

**SAMAGRA GNANA
ESTD. 1988**

**Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University**

Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001, INDIA

+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Shaikh Mohammed Zulfiqar is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “RANDOM WALK HYPOTHESIS OF SELECT CRYPTOCURRENCIES” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Mr. Amith Menezes, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/7/22

DEAN
Prof. Keerthan Raj
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

MSA
SHIPPING (PVT) LTD

REG. OFFICE : TUTICORIN
#118-H & I, South Raja Street,
First Floor, VBMS Tower,
Tuticorin - 628 001, India.
Tel : +91 461 4049333 / 308
E-mail : info@msashipping.com

An ISO 9001:2015
Certified Company

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is certifying that Mr. Vijaya parakashi V Student of "Srinivas University" has done Internship Training at our Organization for the period of March 01st to April 30th, 2022.

Name : Mr. Vijaya parakashi V

Course : Master of Business Administration (LS & SCM Programme)

He was regular in attendance and his Conduct and Character was found to be good during the period of Training with us.

We wish you all success in his future endeavors.....

For MSA Shipping Pvt Ltd.

Authorized Signatory

MUMBAI
Office No. 708, 7th Floor,
Concorde Prominas Co-op. Society Ltd
New No. 40 (Old No. 20)

CHENNAI
Mussala Manor, 8th Floor,
New No. 40 (Old No. 20)
Central Merchant Group.

KANDLA & MUNDRA
Office No. 18, 11, 12, B1 and Kesar Anzali,
Plot 51, Sector 8, Nr. Gandhinagar,
Chamber of Commerce,
Gandhinagar, Mundra

COIMBATORE
#243, First Floor,
Anayikkathi Extension Main Road,
999 to Vasanthi Mills,
Sengavai, Coimbatore - 641 005

TIRUPUR
No. 1, Second Floor,
A.R.P. Complex, 2nd Street,
Ashar Nagar (Near SAP Theatre),
Tirupur - 641 003
Tel : +91 431 433 0075

COCHIN
52/97D, First Floor,
Muttamural Junction,
Kandamully Road, Thiruvalla,
Cochin - 682 013
Tel : +91 484 4034775

DELHI
1 & 2nd Floor,
Cyp. Hubra Apartments Gate,
No. 2, C.A. Park,
New Delhi - 110 013
Tel : +91 11 41074052

MADRASAPATNAM
Room No. 18, B Block, 1st Floor,
Fidelity & DND Commercial Complex,
Gopuram Rd, Madhavapuram,
MADRASAPATNAM, Tamil Nadu - 605 004
Tel : 0420267670

VIJAYAWADA
Office - 40-0-22, 2nd Floor,
Rajawada Road,
Gingee,
Vijayawada - 520 070
Phone : +91 866 000025

28/03/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

Sub: Confirmation of Academic Project

We wish to confirm that Mr. LIBIN RAJ .V(Reg.Num: 2SU20LS815), who is pursuing final year MBA in SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MANGALORE PANDESHWAR, has been offered to do the final year Logistics and Supply chain management project in our concern from 28/03/2022 to 28/06/2022.

As such, your project will include training and focus primarily on learning and developing new skills and gaining a deeper understanding of concepts through hands-on application of the knowledge you learned in class.

For Redova Logistics Pvt Ltd,

Hariharan

Hariharan.N

Recruitment Lead - HR

REDOVA LOGISTICS PRIVATE LIMITED

#43, 8th Cross Street, Thiru-Vi-Ka Industrial Estate, Guindy, Chennai - 32
| www.Redovalogistics.com | Info@Redovalogistics.com |
044 - 22441234

Date:16/06/2022

TO WHOMSOEVER MAY CONCERN

This is certify that Ms.Melisha Dsouza,Reg.No.2SU20MB827,A student of Srinivas University institute of Management and commerce Mangalore, has successfully completed her project study on the topic entitled "A study of Fundamental and Technical Analysis with reference to Selected stocks in Kotak Securities Ltd" in our organisations.

During this period of work, we found her conduct was good and sincere effort to study. We appreciate her effort and interest towards the assigned work.

We wish her all the best for all future endeavours.

For Kotak securities

Sandeep V

Branch Manager

Kotak securities Ltd.

MANDOVI MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED

(AUTHORISED MARUTI SUZUKI DEALER)

Arvind Bldg., Balmatta Road, Hampankatta, Mangalore - 575 001

Service: 0824-2410123, 9845 7 12 365

Fax: 0824-2422877 E-mail: service@mandovi.net Website: www.mandovimotors.in

GSTIN No.: 29AACCM4309H1ZJ C.S.T.: 30167840 dt. 22-02-1999, STC No.: AACC M 4309 H ST001

Ref: MANG/HRD/ 3766/2022-23

Date: 22/07/2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Ms. Mallika C R, studying MBA at Srinivas University, has undergone Project work on "A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction" at our organization in the Month June 2022.

During the tenure we found her to be sincere, hardworking and efficient with good Conduct and aptitude to gain knowledge.

We wish her all the success in her future career.

For Mandovi Motors Private Ltd

For MANDOVI MOTORS PVT. LTD.

Suraj Sapalya
Asst. Manager - HR

Suraj Sapalya

Asst Manager- HR

SERVICE ABOVE SELF

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **MANISH RAI G S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled **“FINANCIAL PLANNING AND TAX SAVING INVESTMENT STRATEGY; A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO SALARIED INDIVIDUAL IN THE CITY OF KASARAGOD”** has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr Niyaz Panakaje, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001
Dean

Place: Mangalore

Date: 29/2/22

Institute Of Management and Commerce,
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore-575001,
+918242421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean,

Institute Of Management & Commerce,
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore - 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. Muhammad Safwan (Reg. No: 2SU20MB822)** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled "**A Study on Risk and Return Analysis of Selected stocks in BSE Sensex**" has been prepared by him in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr Niyaz Panakaje**, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this Institute.

DEAN

Institute of Management and
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575001
(Dean)

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/7/22

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University

Pandeshwar,

Mangalore- 575001, INDIA

Prof . Keerthan Raj

Dean ,

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,

Mangalore-575 001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. LIKHIN K P is a bona- fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022) at a Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study and project titled. "Analysis of the Effectiveness of Budgetary Control Techniques on Organizational Performance with special Reference of CAMPCO LMT Mangalore" has been prepared by her in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree MBA under supervision of Dr Niyaz Panakaje , Assistant Professor & Research Guide , Institute of Management and Commerce , Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this Institute

PROF. KEERTHAN RAJ

DEAN

Institute of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University

Mangaluru - 575 001

Place: Mangalore

Date:

22/2/22

MANDOVI MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED

(AUTHORISED MARUTI SUZUKI DEALER)

Arvind Bldg., Balmatta Road, 'Hampankatta, Mangalore - 575 001

Service: 0824-2410123, 9845 7 12 365

Fax: 0824-2422877 E-mail: service@mandovi.net Website: www.mandovimotors.in

GSTIN No.: 29AACCM4309H1ZI C.S.T.: 30167840 dt. 22-02-1999, STC No.: AACCC M 4309 H ST001

Ref: MANG/HRD/ 3766/2022-23

Date: 22/07/2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Mallika C R**, studying MBA at Srinivas University, has undergone Project work on "A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction" at our organization in the Month June 2022.

During the tenure we found her to be sincere, hardworking and efficient with good Conduct and aptitude to gain knowledge.

We wish her all the success in her future career.

For Mandovi Motors Private Ltd

For MANDOVI MOTORS PVT. LTD.

Suraj Sapalya
Asst. Manager - HR

Suraj Sapalya

Asst Manager- HR

SERVICE ABOVE SELF

Institute of Management and
Commerce Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and
Commerce Srinivas University,
Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Mahammed Sawaz. is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “Impact Of Earning Per Share , and Divident Per Share ,and Price Earning Ratio On Stock Market Performance Of Bombay Stock Exchange” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Dr. Niyaz Panakaje, Assistant Professor & Research Guide, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/7/22

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001, INDIA
+91 824 2421566

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean,
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore – 575001

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **MR. AKSHAY S** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester (2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This internship study & project report titled “AN EVALUATION OF PLASTIC MONEY IN KASARAGOD DISTRICT” has been prepared by her in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of Prof. Abhinandan, Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar of this institute.

PROF. KEERTHAN RAJ
Dean
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

Place: Mangalore
Date: 20/7/22

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Prof. Keerthan Raj

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “A STUDY ON THE IMPLICATION OF BAD BANK IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO NARCL” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Master of Commerce is based on the original work done by Mr. Ahamed Muhsin (2SU20MB803), Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The project has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or any other similar title.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

(Dean)

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Place: Mangalore

Date: 22/1/22

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. Ancy Thomas** is a bona-fide student of MBA 4th semester(2021-2022 Batch) at Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar. This project report titled “**A Case Study On Women Entrepreneurship In Urban Area- Mysuru District**” has been prepared by her in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of MBA under the supervision of **Dr. Sonia Noronhna, Professor,** Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, of this institute.

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Ref. No.	AG16/Project/ANITHA/2022-23	Date	25.07.2022
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CERTIFICATE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to Certify that Miss. **ANITHA** (Reg No: 2SU20MB806), final year MBA(duel) student of Institute of Management And Commerce **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** has done her project work "**INVESTMENT AWARENESS AND OPPORTUNITIES AVAILABLE IN BANKING INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE**" during the period of two months from JAN 31st 2022 to 31st MARCH 2022 under the guidance of Mr. **SUCHETH M D'SOUZA**, Chief Manager, **BANK OF MAHARASHTRA, MANGALORE BRANCH**.

"We wish him all the success in his future endeavours"

For

Bank of Maharashtra

Chief Manager

Mangalore Branch

19388

MAHATMA Group of Institutions
City of Light

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10-JUNE-2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. ANSTON NIXON DSOUZA (Reg.No. 25U20MB807), Final Year Student of MBA (DUAL) Management from Srinivas University College Of Management And Commerce Mangalore, has Undergone Internship at our organization from 02-June-2022 to 04-June-2022 and has completed the project study titled "CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND SALES".

We found him sincere, hardworking and technically sound and result Oriented. He worked well as part of a team during his tenure.

We wish him All the Best in his future endeavors.

For BHARATH AUTO CARS (P) LTD.

Denis Gonsalves
Sr Manager Sales

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